

FAMILY AS AN IMPORTANT LINK IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUNG GENERATION

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: In this article. In family education, it is said that ensuring the cooperation of family, school, neighborhood and community, organizing education with effective use of family traditions, values, work and heroic examples of parents and older generation is an important factor in forming a perfect person.

Keywords: family, school, neighborhood, tradition, value, upbringing, society, purity, spirituality, faith, manners.

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СЕМЬЯ КАК ВАЖНОЕ ЗВЕНО В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПОДРАСТАЮЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ

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Abstract: В этой статье. В семейном воспитании сказано, что обеспечение сотрудничества семьи, школы, соседства и общины, организация воспитания с эффективным использованием семейных традиций, ценностей, труда и героического примера родителей и старшего поколения является важным фактором формирования совершенной личности.

Keywords: семья, школа, соседство, традиция, ценность, воспитание, общество, чистота, духовность, вера, нравы.

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YOSH AVLOD TARBIYASIDA OILA MUHIM BO`G'IN SIFATIDA

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada . Oila tarbiyasida oila, maktab, mahalla va jamoatchilik hamkorligini ta'minlash, oila an'analari, qadriyatlari, ota-ona va keksa avlodning mehnat va qahramonlik namunalaridan samarali foydalangan holda tarbiyani tashkil etish komil insonni shakllantirishda muhim omili ekanligi haqida so'z boradi.

Keywords: oila, maktab, mahalla, an'ana, qadriyat, tarbiya, jamiyat, soflik, ma'naviyat, e'tiqod, odo, axloq.

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The family is the first and primary link of the society. Society is made up of these small particles. The third world, which emerged from the union of two living beings, two worlds, is a family. The family should be based on purity and purity, mutual love and loyalty. This is an important factor for raising children. A set of skills for a person's spirituality, worldview, beliefs are mainly formed in the family.

Therefore, the role of family spirituality in the education of young people is incomparable. The role of the family in raising a spiritually mature person is huge. In fact, the family is a part of society. All the processes taking place in the society directly affect the family and people's way of life. Every person is nourished from the sources of spirituality in the family itself, starting from his youth.

First of all, the role of parents in the family, their relationship with other family members is a school for the child. Interactions between family members, regardless of what system it is, should correspond to the process of interaction between members of society. The relationship between the members of the society is defined and managed by laws, rules, and discipline, and this is reflected in the family as well. In the management of family relations, parents and older people have a special role. A person lives under the influence of his family throughout his life. It not only forms individual and social skills, but also forms parenting skills for establishing mutual relations. Especially the family is a decisive factor in the formation of the spiritual activity of a person. Traditions and customs that have been passed down from generation to generation in the family for centuries are continued and instilled in each family member. For example, in the family, mutual respect is embedded in everyone's blood. In the family, the opinion of older people always plays a decisive role. They must be respected. There are traditions such as welcoming elderly people to the house, blessing them, being the first to shake hands at the table, or listening when an elderly person is speaking, which should be done by every family member. Customs such as respect for parents and respect between other family members are the cornerstones of the Uzbek family.

The backbone of the family. In the minds of our children, feelings of love for the country and the Motherland are formed in the family, in the neighborhood where they live. The country's future, peace and prosperity depends first of all on our children growing up in this small community. As long as education is well established in any family and neighborhood, that family and neighborhood will prosper.

Many people think about the question of when to start raising a child. Many scholars have given different answers to it. In particular, Ibn Sina answered that it is necessary to deal with the education of a child before its birth, starting from the mother's womb.

Paying attention to family, morals and education is one of our duties that is ingrained in our blood. The proverb "One child has seven neighboring parents" is typical of our nation. This proverb itself shows how important it is for us to raise children and family. The people of the neighborhood, especially the elderly, never passed by a child doing a dirty job on the street, and immediately reprimanded him and called him to the right path. After all, our holy religion, which commands to be

beautiful, polite, and well-behaved in every way, and to purify the soul, gives great importance to the family.

The atmosphere in the family is stable when parents feel their responsibilities. In order for children to grow up to be polite, the neighborhood, along with the parents, is a great school of example. It is not for nothing that our people say that "birds do what they see in their nests". A parent raising a child should be able to show noble qualities in every movement, posture, behavior and interaction with others. Because the child is extremely imitative and observant by nature. Therefore, the people around him influence them with their habits, sometimes without realizing it. Rough relationships in the family, a lot of lying, unpleasant behavior create an unhealthy environment that negatively affects the upbringing of a child.

Another method that parents can use as a tool to teach their child to spend time effectively is the wise use of modern information technologies.

It is important for parents to take children with them to scenic places in nature, to museums, and at the same time inculcate the grace of beauty in their hearts in order to form a sense of aesthetic education and enjoyment of beautiful landscapes.

The family is the main foundation for a person to find his place in life, to be respected in the country, and to embody high moral rules.

Educating young people mentally and physically is a priority of our state's policy. The foundation of education is laid in the family. Education is a complex and long-lasting unique process, which begins long before the birth of a child. That is, the future parents' health, lineage, outlook, inner and outer world, morals, compatibility of material and spiritual level, spiritual and physical readiness for marriage are important in the upbringing of the future child.

Ensuring cooperation of family, school, neighborhood and community in family upbringing, organization of upbringing with effective use of family traditions, values, examples of work and heroism of parents and older generation is an important factor in forming a perfect person.

For today's youth, it is the highest value to show selflessness for family, nation, people, destiny of the Motherland, today and tomorrow. It is the duty of us adults to the society to treat the youth of the new century not as an object of education, but as a subject. Communicating with them as equals, like-minded, close sympathizers, listening to their thoughts and personal views on the events and phenomena happening in the family and in the environment, plays an important role in raising free-thinking generations for our society.

To effectively organize the free time of young people in the family, to educate them through mental and physical work, to form national consciousness and pride through the commonality of national and universal values, to express their identity,

to increase their responsibility for their duties and responsibilities before the family, the nation, and the Motherland. , being aware of their outlook, lifestyle, thoughts and opinions should become one of the main directions of activity of every parent, official state and public organizations.

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